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In today's reality, information technologies are used across all sectors of social production, serving as key tools in managing all types of organizations. Their advantages are particularly evident in the practices of commercial enterprises. Presently, information is considered one of the most valuable economic resources, and the effectiveness of its processing through modern ICT directly determines the future performance of an enterprise. Consequently, investing in information assets has become one of the most promising directions for investment activity [2].

In practice, the rapid pace of scientific and technological development, increasing complexity of enterprise operations, and the growth of information volumes necessitate more efficient data processing and utilization—tasks that are becoming increasingly challenging.

Global market conditions introduce numerous challenges that every enterprise must face. Achieving business process objectives depends primarily on operating conditions. Companies are continuously influenced by environmental changes and competing firms striving to expand their market presence by improving product and service quality. As a result, enterprises are compelled to focus their efforts on maintaining a stable and competitive position, making rational strategic decisions, and achieving economic goals through financial and managerial efficiency analysis and monitoring.

Controlling and analyzing financial performance is essential for successful business management. It enables companies to prevent crises, insolvency, and bankruptcy. Assessing the financial and operational activities of enterprises provides insights into market standing and supports the formulation of sound management decisions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The effectiveness of an organization's operations is closely tied to the ability of its management bodies to fulfill their responsibilities and implement management functions effectively at all levels to achieve strategic goals. Let us consider several definitions of the concept of "efficiency." The renowned economist Peter Drucker relates the concept of efficiency to the ability to achieve results with minimal resource usage [3]. CIS economist E.M. Korotkov views enterprise efficiency as a result of managerial competence, decision-making strategies, strategic approaches, management quality, and monitoring practices [4].

In local literature, it is important to explore the historical origins of the term "efficiency." It was first used by classical economist D. Ricardo in 1817 in the theory of comparative advantage. The term also appears in the works of V. Pareto, whose interpretations have contributed to ongoing academic debates [5]. A.B. Borisov's *Great Economic Dictionary* interprets efficiency as the effectiveness of a process, based on the perspectives of Ricardo and Pareto [6]. All three scholars connect the notion of effectiveness with efficiency.

Another viewpoint comes from foreign economist L.A. Naskina, who differentiates between these terms by suggesting that the ratio of outcomes to costs—referred to as the efficiency coefficient—should be associated with productivity, while effectiveness reflects the correctness of the chosen direction [7].

Foreign scholars R.S. Kaplan and D.P. Norton extensively discuss enterprise efficiency and economic performance within the framework of strategic management systems [8]. Their focus is on the core features of strategic systems and their evaluation methods. I. Ansoff emphasizes studying the prospects of enterprises and assessing influencing factors, noting the need to forecast and apply extrapolation techniques due to inherent risks in long-term operations [9]. M. Porter highlights the significance of innovation in enterprise development, stressing that sustainable growth and competitive advantage can only be achieved through continuous innovation [10].

A group of national economists – R.S. Muratov, I.A. Djalolova, and S.Sh. Oripov – have thoroughly examined the enterprise as an independent entity, exploring its nature, the requirements imposed on it, indicator systems, financial stability, and governance issues [11]. They also assessed management models, principles, and standards applicable to enterprises.

In the views of economists I.O. Ulashev and Sh.A. Atamuradov, the challenges of enterprise management mechanisms, their solutions, choice of optimal management strategies, and assessment of managerial efficiency are explored [12]. G.Sh. Khonkeldieva, in her research, focuses on corporate governance, evaluation of organizational and economic indicators, motivation systems, and strategies for enhancing efficiency [13].

At the micro level, a widely accepted approach to identifying the components of economic security is proposed by foreign economist M.V. Alyabyeva [14], who classifies its elements as intellectual personnel, financial, technical-technological, political-legal, environmental, informational, and managerial. A similar classification is provided by V.V. Shlikov [15]. A.P. Kozyrev [16], by adding market and interface components, limits his model to four key dimensions that reflect the reliability of relationships with economic agents: social, financial, production, and sales. R.A. Moshkova justifies the inclusion of socio-economic, financial, production,

environmental, energy, organizational-managerial, material-technical, and informational-legal components in the structure of economic security [17].

T.V. Ziryanova analyzes economic security across various hierarchical levels of the economy, outlines its functional characteristics, and highlights the key factors ensuring the enterprise life cycle: financial stability, competitiveness, management efficiency, protection of the information environment, legal safeguards, personnel and property security, and commercial interests [18].

According to N.A. Denisova, components that are not of an economic nature – such as financial, internal, external, and socio-economic factors – should not be included in the economic security structure [19]. L.K. Ivanova also asserts that non-economic elements should be excluded from the components of economic security [20].

Thus, the components of enterprise economic security can include marketing, innovation, production (technical and technological), socio-economic, and financial dimensions. All of these components are interrelated and interdependent, possessing a systemic character. Moreover, economic security also encompasses elements related to products (works, services), where revenue generation and profit – after deducting expenses – are directly tied to the enterprise's economic activities and relationships.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research article provides a theoretical analysis of the role of information and communication technologies (ICT) in ensuring management efficiency and security in enterprises. The study is based on theoretical methods, including literature analysis, synthesis, generalization, and logical reasoning.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Under modern conditions, enterprises face the constant challenge of monitoring technologically complex markets while improving production and service quality. Since traditional efficiency evaluations are often limited to internal performance indicators, gross profit, and customer satisfaction levels, they do not fully reflect a comprehensive picture of service effectiveness. Therefore, the proposed recommendations for establishing an activity evaluation system offer a practical solution for enterprises to address this issue effectively and optimize performance assessment (figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Indicators and criteria for assessing the quality of provided services¹

Figure 2. Evaluation system considering enterprise performance efficiency²

¹ The figure was developed by the author

² The figure was developed by the author

It is well known that the ultimate goal of increasing the efficiency of enterprise potential utilization is to achieve positive outcomes. Accordingly, effective use of economic security potential results in the formation of the enterprise's economic security, which includes a set of measures aimed at protecting each of its components.

Therefore, the information component plays a key role in ensuring the economic security of a business entity. Figure 3 illustrates the main components of enterprise economic security, along with the essence and functions of ensuring information security (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Tools for Ensuring Enterprise Economic Security³

One of the most essential components of an enterprise's economic security structure is the creation of a unified system of information about its operations. A key responsibility of management is to develop and implement measures to ensure this system.

When studying enterprise information security as an object of administrative and legal protection, the approach of scholar N.A. Lukashuk is noteworthy. According to his view, the concept of "information security in entrepreneurial activity" refers to a defined set of measures aimed at ensuring the protection of information at an appropriate level (Figure 4).

³ The figure was developed by the author

Figure 4. Directions for Ensuring Enterprise Economic Security⁴

Normative-legal documents regulating entrepreneurial activity and defining the specific features of data protection by business entities represent an internal set of rules within a particular enterprise. These rules are aimed at protecting information resources, ensuring the effective operation of the business entity's information system, and neutralizing or eliminating threats to its overall functioning.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, enterprise information security is supported by legal measures that define the legal field and the rights and responsibilities of stakeholders, particularly within the framework of the state's information policy. This includes:

- Organizational support, which establishes rules and procedures for receiving and processing information within the enterprise;
- Technical support, which involves tools that enable the protection of information through technical means;
- Software and hardware solutions, which allow the implementation of secure decision-making and safeguard systems.

It should be emphasized that legal support is formed at the national level, while at the enterprise level, it entails the development and implementation of internal regulations on information security. These may include:

- Identification of trade secret objects;
- Measures for secure information storage;
- Liability for unauthorized disclosure.

To ensure the effective functioning of organizational support, the accounting system plays a crucial role by recording key facts of economic activity.

⁴ The figure was developed by the author

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